

Obtaining the Tsallis Distribution from $e/T \ll 1$ and $e/T \gg 1$ Considerations? Part 2

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In Part I, we suggested that the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution arises from the $e/T \ll 1$ expansion of the unnormalized Tsallis distribution for any q . In other words, it might suggest that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution holds for small deviations of energies from e_{ave} if one changes e/T to $(e - e_{ave})/T$. When e begins to move away from e_{ave} significantly, a factor q is introduced to show that the Maxwell-Boltzmann case no longer holds. This factor is introduced such that for $q=1$ one recovers the MB distribution regardless of the value of $(e - e_{ave})/T$. We thus suggest here that one way of interpreting the Tsallis distribution is that it shows a change from a Maxwell-Boltzmann one as deviations from equilibrium values are no longer small. In other words, the MB case does not hold for all energies, only those close to e_{ave} .

We point out that it is known that the MB distribution is an approximation of the microcanonical case and that it replaces the constraint E_{total} with $E_{total} = \sum_i e_i f(e_i)$. In other words, a single particle (of N , where N is large) can have more energy than T_{total} (which is unphysical, but not a real problem because $\exp(-e/T)$ is so small in such a case). We argue that the Tsallis distribution may be seen as an approach aimed at correcting the breakdown of the Maxwell-Boltzmann picture for energies which deviate too much from e_{ave} . The MB distribution is like an equilibrium consisting only of small deviations from e_{ave} . This seems to be similar in notion to the idea of a mechanical equilibrium about a stationary point. If one expands a potential $V(x)$, the first order term is 0 due to the stationary requirement and the second is of the order x^2 (an oscillator) as long as x is not too big. We suggest this analogy because in (1), the authors note that the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann factor for a potential $V(x)$, i.e. $\exp(-V(x)/T)$, leads to the Tsallis distribution if $dV/dx = ax / (1+bx^2)$. We argue that if $\sqrt{a}=b$, then $V(x) = 1/(2a) \ln(1+ax^2)$. For x very small, one has an oscillator potential, i.e. $\exp(-ax^2/T)$. One might argue physically that such an oscillator solution breaks down (because one no longer has an oscillator when x increases) and that the Tsallis distribution is an attempt at dealing with a breakdown of MB statistics for deviations from equilibrium results which become too large.

Tsallis Distribution and Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

It is well-known that the Tsallis entropy: $S_T = 1/(1-q) \{1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q\}$ ((1a))

and the Tsallis unnormalized distribution: $\{1 - (1-q)e/T\}^{1/(1-q)}$ ((1b))

both yield Maxwell-Boltzmann results for $q=1$, using l'Hopital's rule.

In Part I, we suggested that perhaps a more important link with the MB distribution arises in the $e/T \ll 1$ limit if one writes:

$$\exp(1/(1-q) \ln(1-(1-q)e/T)) \approx \exp(-e/T) \quad ((2))$$

One does not have to worry about the value of q in the $e/T \ll 1$ limit.

We ask here whether this implies that the Tsallis distribution allows for one to have the MB case for e/T or rather $(e-e_{ave})/T \ll 1$? In such a scenario, the MB distribution would apply to small deviations from the average picture e_{ave} , but not to larger deviations. In the Tsallis model, $q(e-e_{ave})/T$ would then appear and affect larger deviations.

From a physical point of view, we point out that it is known that the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario deviates from the microcanonical one. It is the microcanonical one which correctly restricts total energy to a single number while the MB case uses:

$$E_{ave} = E_{total} = \sum_i f(e_i) e_i \quad \text{where } f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is only an approximation which allows for simple math. It is further known that the MB scenario allows the energy E_{total} to be distributed among N particles such that any distribution carries the same probability weight. This is an assumption as far as we know and is not necessarily completely correct.

If one considers a scattering approach to obtaining the MB distribution, then:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((4b))$$

One takes \ln of ((4b)) and equates with $-1/T$ multiplied by ((4a)). Again, ((4a)) and ((4b)) suggest that the only physical consideration for an interaction to occur is the presence of a particle with e_i which is presumed to be proportional to the number of particles present. We have already suggested that the speed of a particle may affect the number of collisions it may induce in a certain amount of time. Thus, it might be the case that ((4a)) and ((4b)) are only valid for small deviations from an average value.

If this is the case, the idea of $(e-e_{ave})/T \ll 1$ yielding the MB distribution may have physical implications. The Tsallis distribution might then be an attempt to describe larger deviations from e_{ave} , albeit in a rather simple manner by weighting $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$ by the factor q . A priori, there is no reason why this should be the correct distribution for all situations which deviate from the MB case for deviations of $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$ which are no longer $\ll 1$, but at least it provides a model for such a case.

Analogy with Mechanical Equilibrium

In (1), it is noted that given a potential $V(x)$, the MB spatial distribution is:

$$\exp(-V(x)/T) \quad ((5))$$

The author of (1) points out that one obtains a Tsallis distribution from ((5)) if:

$$dV/dx = ax / (1+bx) \quad ((6))$$

We consider the case of $b=aa$. Then one may integrate ((6)) to find that:

$$V(x) = \frac{1}{2a} \ln(1+axx) \quad ((7))$$

In the limit of $axx \ll 1$, $V(x)$ is proportional to $\frac{1}{2}axx$, i.e. an oscillator ((8)).

It is known that an oscillator solution applies to a small deviation from a stable equilibrium for any potential. One might suggest that this is the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, i.e. $\exp(-.5axx)$. If deviations become larger, the oscillator assumption breaks down and one requires a different result. In this case, one might suggest a Tsallis form. Thus, once again the Tsallis picture seems to show the change from a Maxwell-Boltzmann one for idealized equilibrium to a less idealized one, i.e. the Tsallis case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I we showed that the unnormalized Tsallis distribution: $\{1 - (1-q) e/T\}^{1/(1-q)}$ yields the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann result $\exp(-e/T)$ for any q for $e/T \ll 1$. Here we argue that this may imply that the MB case holds strictly for small deviations from equilibrium, if one replaces e_i/T with $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$. As deviations become larger, a different statistical view is needed perhaps. The Tsallis view uses the idea of enhancing $(e_i - e_{ave})/T$ with a factor q . This, we argue, is one possible way of dealing with deviations which are not tiny compared to equilibrium (average) values.

We note that in (1) it is argued that the MB spatial case, $\exp(-V(x)/T)$, for a potential $V(x)$, yields the Tsallis form if: $dV/dx = ax/(1+bx)$. We show that for $b=aa$, one obtains $\frac{1}{2a} \ln(1+axx) = V(x)$. For $axx \ll 1$, this is an oscillator potential. We argue that this is like an oscillating solution about a stationary stable point for any $V(x)$. If axx , however, is no longer $\ll 1$, then a different solution appears. In other words, we restrict the MB case to that of small deviations from the average.

References

- 1 Hilhorst, H.J. Central Limit Theorems for Correlated Variables: Some Critical Remarks 2024 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0901.1249>